

THE ORGANIZATION OF ISLAMIC COOPERATION (OIC) AS A SUBJECT OF ISLAMIC DIPLOMACY AND INTERNATIONAL LAW

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ABSTRACT

The article examines the legal status, structure and activities of the Organization of Islamic Cooperation (OIC) as a unique subject of Islamic diplomacy and international law. Its function in conflict prevention, peace consolidation, protection of the rights of Muslims and the development of peaceful dialogue are analyzed. Special attention is paid to the OIC's interaction with the United Nations (UN) and its role in shaping the Islamic model of peaceful dispute settlement.

Introduction. The modern system of international relations is characterized by a high degree of political, cultural and religious interdependence. Under these conditions, regional and religiously oriented international organizations play an increasingly significant role, among which the Organization of Islamic Cooperation occupies a special place – it is the second largest international structure after the UN in terms of membership. Established in 1969, the OIC unites 57 states with a large number of Muslims as well as represents the collective will of the Islamic world to strengthen peace, justice and mutual respect. Its activities are based both on the norms of Islamic law and other principles of modern international law, which makes the OIC a unique bridge between the Islamic legal tradition and global diplomacy.

The OIC was established at the Conference of the Heads of Muslim States held in Rabat. Its founding document is the Charter of the OIC, adopted in 1972 and revised in 2008 (Dakar). According to the Charter, the OIC is an intergovernmental organization endowed with international legal personality with the right to conclude treaties and represent the interests of its member states in the international arena.

The activities of the OIC are based on the concept of Islamic diplomacy, which presupposes the peaceful settlement of international disputes in the spirit of justice (*adl*), mutual understanding (*tafahum*) and reconciliation (*sulh*).

Key principles of Islamic diplomacy enshrined in the OIC Charter:

- Rejection of the use of force and violence;
- Respect for sovereignty and territorial integrity of states;
- Non-interference in internal affairs;
- Settlement of conflicts through negotiations and mediation;

- Protection of the rights of Muslim minorities and communities.

These norms largely coincide with the principles of the UN Charter (1945), particularly in the areas concerning the maintenance of international peace and security.¹

The OIC established a Permanent Committee for Peacekeeping and Conflict Resolution, as well as Department of Political Affairs, which operates in close cooperation with the UN, African Union and League of Arab States². Of particular importance is the OIC's contribution to shaping international norms against extremism and terrorism, enriched in the Cairo Declaration on Human Rights³ and the OIC Ten-Year Program of Action on Combating Terrorism.

An important initiative was the establishment of the International Islamic Peacebuilding Commission in 2011, which promotes the fulfillment of international obligations of Muslim states in the fields of peace and security.

Thus, the OIC combines Islamic legal values with the mechanisms of international law, making it a unique example of a religious-legal subject in global diplomacy.

To conclude, the OIC occupies a special place in the system of international relations, representing a synthesis of Islamic diplomacy and international legal principles. Its activities are aimed at preventing conflicts, building trust, protecting the right of Muslim people and promoting the ideals of justice and peace. The OIC not only reflects the political unity of the Islamic world, but also makes a significant contribution to the development of international law, demonstrating the possibility of harmoniously combining religious and universal legal values. In the face of modern challenges – the rise of extremism, ethno-religious conflicts and crisis of trust between states – the experience and instruments of the OIC represent an important resource for building a sustainable and just global order.

References:

1. Charter of the Organization of Islamic Cooperation, Dakar, 2008
2. Cairo Declaration on Human Rights in Islam, Organization of the Islamic Conference. 1990
3. United Nations Charter, San Francisco, 1945
4. Resolution 60/1 of the UN General Assembly, 2005 World Summit Outcome
5. Esposito J.L. (ed.) The Oxford Encyclopedia of the Modern Islamic World. Oxford University Press, 2001
6. <https://www.un.org/en/>
7. <https://www.oic-oci.org/>

¹ Resolution 60/1 of the UN General Assembly, 2005 World Summit Outcome

² <http://www.leagueofarabstates.net/en/Pages/default.aspx>

³ The Cairo Declaration on Human Rights in Islam, 1990

[https://elearning.icrc.org/detention/en/story_content/external_files/Human%20Rights%20in%20Islam%20\(1990\).](https://elearning.icrc.org/detention/en/story_content/external_files/Human%20Rights%20in%20Islam%20(1990).)